

Dopaminergic Midbrain reaction in Information Seeking Behaviour

Introduction:

The activities and channels a person uses after determining his or her information needs and using the information that is subsequently acquired can be characterized as information seeking behavior under the field of information science. Concerns about how people use information in their workplaces are the driving force for research on information-seeking behavior. A perceived need leads to information seeking behavior, whereby the information user places demands on formal or informal information sources or services to meet the need, with varying degrees of success (Wilson 1999:251).

Definition:

Information seeking behaviour is "A need perceived by an information user, who, in order to satisfy that need, makes demands upon formal or informal information sources or services, which results in success or failure to find relevant information"

For many years, the main focus of research for information and computer science scholars has focused on information needs and information seeking. It is widely accepted that a user's information requirement is the first step in the information-seeking process. Over the past three decades, a significant amount of literature has been written, and an extensive amount of study has been done on users' information needs and information-seeking behaviors.

Physiological Aspect:

- Information seeking behaviour is a fundamental process of human brain that is closely related with learning and problem solving. It is related to physiological constructs. A librarian or researcher may not observe it , only manifestations of the need of information can be observed.
- The user may require rapid and concise information and extensive information to achieve a goal, such as solving a problem, answering a particular query, or satisfying a curiosity. There are different processes are technological and related to the information retrieval system, user

interfaces, and so on. Other processes relate to the nature and characteristics of the content as well as the individual user.

- The process may take more or less time, and may become simple or complex depending on the nature of the users. The type of nature may be with the psychological aspect of a user but it depends on the neurons and hormones of the biological aspect.

Midbrain region:

- Midbrain dopamine neurons, also referred to as dopaminergic neurons in the ventral mesodiencephalon (mdDA), are a class of neurons that are essential for regulating emotion, motivating behaviour, establishing associations with rewarding stimuli, regulating movement and paying attention to salient environmental stimuli. The basic behaviour of animals depends on these neurons functioning properly.
- A complicated behaviour, information-seeking promotes intellectual growth, is essential to social relationships, and is necessary for learning, decision-making, and goal-directed processing.
- Learning is a process which can be changed in any response to a particular stimulus. Memory is a modification of a cell which mediates that change. The molecules of signal provide links between stimuli that lead to synaptic action which changes into responsiveness of the cell to stimuli. Dopamine is involved in reward related incentive or provoking behaviour.

Source:

Dopamine controlling cell which develops from a single embryonic cell group. The cell groups originates from the mesencephalic and diencephalic areas of the midbrain region.

Examples:

Approach, consumption, and addiction are examples of reward-seeking behaviours that are tightly linked to DA.

As a result of reward excitement, neurons that produce DA fire, which is a motivating substance. This theory is supported by data showing that when a

reward exceeds expectations, specific dopaminergic neurons fire more frequently, increasing motivation or desire for the reward.

The urge to learn is a typical definition of curiosity, which is a basic aspect of human nature. It shows itself among individuals as information-seeking behaviors including reading, asking questions, doing experiments, and searching the internet. Such conduct is essential to decision-making, social interaction, and learning.

The mesolimbic dopaminergic:

Numerous forms of reward, motivated actions, and, more recently, cognitive functions have all been linked to the mesolimbic dopaminergic (ML-DA) system. Functional theories have highlighted DA's role in learning reinforcement and promotion as well as in coordinating goal-directed activities. The potential of the ML-DA system to trigger an instinctive emotional appetitive state (SEEKING), which developed to cause creatures to seek out all types of life-supporting stimuli and to avoid damages, is how the affective neuroethological approach provided here interprets the system.

The argument that the SEEKING disposition arises through the functional integration of ventral basal ganglia (BG) into thalamocortical processes is followed by a description of the anatomical framework in which the ML system is embedded. When expressed at the motor level, DA transmission facilitates the "release" of neuronal activity patterns that cause active SEEKING behaviors by filtering cortical and limbic input that spreads into BG. The incorporation of cognitive and perceptual representations in the expanded networks of the SEEKING desire is achieved through the neurodynamic process of reverberation of these patterns. This is how the SEEKING disposition affects anticipatory predictions, associative learning, incentive salience, and attention.

Principal regions of the forebrain that the mesolimbic DA system reaches. The structures innervated by ML-DA have been classified into diencephalic, basal forebrain, and upper forebrain areas based on morphological and evolutionary factors.

Fig : Mesolimbic dopaminergic (ML-DA) system

(Source : Alcaro, A., Huber, R., & Panksepp, J. (2007). Behavioral functions of the mesolimbic dopaminergic system: An affective neuroethological perspective. *Brain Research Reviews*, 56(2), 283–321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainresrev.2007.07.014>)

Studies using localized electrical brain stimulation have linked the ML-DA to both appetitively motivated behaviors and positive rewarding experiences. DA seems to encourage widespread behavioral arousal in both good and negative emotional states, possibly best understood as the pursuit of safety, since it is also released in reaction to stress and aversive stimuli.

Only the ML-DA system projects to the frontal cortex, but all ascending mesencephalic DA projections innervate the BG relatively extensively. Despite growing interest in the DA transmission in the frontal brain.

Fig : The releasing of DA

(Source : Alcaro, A., Huber, R., & Panksepp, J. (2007). Behavioral functions of the mesolimbic dopaminergic system: An affective neuroethological perspective. *Brain Research Reviews*, 56(2), 283–321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.brainresrev.2007.07.014>)

Since information-seeking and reward-seeking share a brain system, there is inherent value in the chance to learn new things. Correlational studies that demonstrate that the chance to learn is encoded in areas rich in dopaminergic neurons and their targets (such as the Orbital Frontal Cortex and Nucleus Accumbens) lend credence to this theory. For instance, dopamine-rich brain areas have been found to exhibit information prediction error signals, which are thought to promote information seeking in a manner similar to reward prediction errors.

These signals support the theory that the brain views the chance to learn as a higher order reward because they have been shown even in cases where the information is non-instrumental—that is, it cannot be employed to prevent

future damage or obtain benefits. Since information may prove useful in the future even if it seems useless now, such coding may be adaptive.

Dopamine may therefore enhance information-seeking, according to one theory. The impact of valence on information-seeking, however, may also be selectively influenced by dopamine. It has been demonstrated that people are more interested in information regarding potential benefits than losses.

Monkeys prefer to know ahead of time the size of rewards they are about to receive, especially when they expect large rewards; some people refuse to receive the results of medical tests out of fear of receiving bad news; and investors monitor their portfolio more frequently when they expect their worth to have increased rather than decreased. It has been demonstrated that valence-dependent dopaminergic midbrain areas in humans code for the chance to receive information.

Gaining information depends on neural activity in critical ways:

One important distinction is whether the brain activity under investigation is associated with the decision to get advance knowledge or with the anticipation of such information. Neural activity associated with the information-seeking decision can be examined in certain studies where individuals have a choice about whether to obtain the advance information at a cost (e.g., paying money, giving up some juice, or waiting longer for the information). Conversely, other research has concentrated on information-expectation-related activity instead than choice-related activity. Despite the seeming subtlety of this distinction, a mechanical explanation of information-seeking behavior is essential.

Whether the advance information is instrumental or non-instrumental is another important distinction.

- **Instrumental Behaviour :**

This conduct may influence future results and serve as a roadmap for future behaviors.

Examples: A coffee lover on a brief business trip to a foreign country for the first time can care about the quality of their morning coffee and want to visit a shop that will provide a good cup of coffee. Since they have no direct experience with any shops in town, they may use online reviews to gather information about various shops before selecting one to visit. Information seeking is essential to our daily decision-making and can take many different forms depending on the context .

- **Non Instrumental Behaviour :**

It cannot be used in any way to significantly impact future results.

Examples:

The coffee enthusiast must now begin gaining experiences with various cafes again after moving to a new place where their prior knowledge is no longer useful. For a period, they might explore more than normal, going to various stores multiple times until they discover a new favorite and begin going there frequently. Last but not least, the coffee lover's curiosity about coffee culture may extend beyond the places they visit or dwell; they may read blogs and social media posts about coffee shops worldwide even if they do not currently have any plans to visit those locations.

Fig : Information gathering in various decision-making scenarios

(Source : Jin, H., Wang, H., Gong, C., & Liu, L. (2018). A study on the influencing factors of consumer information-seeking behavior in the context of ambient intelligence. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 11(4), 1397–1404. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-018-1005-y>)

Social Epistemology related with information seeking behaviour

A subfield of philosophy known as social epistemology studies how knowledge is produced, shared, and validated in communities. It looks at how groups of people shape our understanding of knowledge, how social institutions and interactions shape the process of knowing, and how knowledge is socially produced. Conversely, information seeking behavior (ISB) describes how people look for, collect, and apply information to fulfill their requirements or address issues. Despite coming from distinct disciplines, these two domains are closely related since they both deal with the creation, sharing, and consuming of knowledge.

Understanding social epistemology

Fundamentally, social epistemology is concerned with the ways in which knowledge is obtained, validated, and disseminated within societies. It makes the case that comprehending knowledge needs more than merely looking at individual cognition and places emphasis on the social processes that shape knowledge. It takes into account how knowledge is created, shared, and accepted by taking into account elements including institutions, media, technology, cultural norms, and group dynamics.

The idea that knowledge is a social practice rather than only an individual endeavor is central to social epistemology. For example, ordinary knowledge is influenced by social interactions and cultural expectations, whereas scientists operate inside groups that share norms for knowledge validation. People in these societies learn what they know, what they trust, and how they obtain information because of the communal nature of knowledge.

Fig : Epistemology relation

(source : Maton, Karl. (2000). Languages of Legitimation: The structuring significance for intellectual fields of strategic knowledge claims. British Journal of Sociology of Education - BRIT J SOCIOL EDUC. 21. 147-167. 10.1080/713655351.)

The Intersection of Social Epistemology and ISB (Information Seeking Behaviour):

- **Social Influence on Information Seeking:** According to social epistemology, knowledge is intricately linked to social situations rather than being independently of individuals. The sources of information, the ways in which people obtain it, and the ways in which they assess its reliability are all impacted by social circumstances, making this extremely pertinent to information seeking behavior. People frequently rely on other people to provide them with information, whether that information comes from formal sources like specialists, media consumption, or peer guidance. Both the direction and the kind of information sought can be influenced by these social interactions. In this sense, ISB is a socially mediated activity as well as an individual cognitive process.
- **Knowledge Validation and Information Organizations:** Social epistemology emphasizes the role that communities play in confirming and approving knowledge. This is clear in ISB, where people frequently turn to reputable professionals or members of the community for information. Whether in a casual social network (e.g., friends discussing the latest news) or a professional community (e.g., medical practitioners consulting research journals), the veracity and reliability of information are frequently socially negotiated. People's information-seeking behavior can be influenced by this community component of knowledge validation, which directs people toward sources that are approved or supported by a social group.
- **Social Trustworthiness and Knowledge Evaluation:** Social epistemology and information-seeking behavior both depend heavily on trust. People in an epistemic environment that is socially created

frequently rely on reliable institutions or sources to direct their information-seeking activities. Social epistemology places a strong emphasis on the importance of trust in the sharing of knowledge, especially in fields that are unclear or complex. From deciding where to look for information to figuring out how to judge its dependability, information-seekers' behavior can be greatly influenced by their tendency to place greater trust in sites that are recommended by their social networks.

- **Institutional and Cultural Effects on Knowledge Seeking:** Social epistemology emphasizes how larger institutional and cultural institutions influence knowledge. Regarding ISB, these structures have the power to affect people's search behavior as well as the type of information they look for. For instance, people may consult scholarly sources for information on technology or health in a culture that places a high value on scientific knowledge. On the other hand, people may rely more on family members or community elders for information in cultures that value firsthand knowledge and local expertise. Institutional contexts, like libraries or research centers, also produce settings where professional standards and practices influence how people access information.

Conclusion

Since both study how knowledge is obtained, disseminated, and assessed in social contexts, social epistemology and information-seeking behavior are closely related. Social, cultural, and institutional elements have a significant impact on information seeking behavior, which is not solely an individual cognitive activity. We can better understand how knowledge is created and shared in society by looking at how communities, trust, and social validation influence the information-seeking process. This junction emphasizes how crucial it is to take social factors into account when researching how people look for, interpret, and use information in a world that is becoming more interconnected by the day.

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